

Synthesis and Cardiovascular Activity of Piperidyl Ethyl Indoles

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Some new 2-substituted-N-(substituted piperidyl) indole-3-yl-glyoxylamides and 2-substituted-3-[β -{N-(substituted piperidyl)} ethyl] indoles have been synthesized as possible cardiovascular agents by the condensation of different piperidines with indole glyoxylchloride followed by reduction with lithium aluminium hydride in anhydrous dimethoxyethane.

INDOLE derivatives have been reported to possess marked antihypertensive activity¹⁻⁶. Several benzamidopiperidyl ethyl indoles have been reported as cardiovascular agents^{7,8}. Recently indoramin-3-2-(4-benzamidopiperid-1-yl)-ethyl indole has been found to possess sustained hypotensive, antihistaminic and adrenoceptor blocking activities and is used clinically in man⁹⁻¹².

With a view to study the effect of other functional variants on hypotensive activity we have synthesized a series of 2-substituted-N-(substituted piperidyl) indole-3-glyoxylamides and 2-substituted-3-[β -{N-(substituted piperidyl)} ethyl] indoles and evaluated them for their cardiovascular activity. The compounds were synthesized according to the route given below :

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Compounds were routinely checked for their homogeneity by TLC on Silica Gel G. Infrared spectra (ν_{\max} in cm^{-1}) was recorded on Perkin Elmer infracord 137. Substituted indoles were prepared according to known procedures^{13,14}. Substituted indoleglyoxylchlorides were prepared following the reported methods^{15,16}.

2-Substituted-N'-(Substituted piperidyl)-indole-3-yl glyoxylamides :

To substituted indoleglyoxylchloride (0.01 mole) in dry benzene (50 ml), substituted piperidine (0.01 mole) was added slowly. The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 8 hrs and the benzene distilled off. The residue was washed with pet ether and recrystallized from DMF-water. The m.p.s, yields and other analytical data of the synthesized compounds are given in Table 1. Compounds No. 2, 6 and 7 in table 1 showed characteristic bands of—NH stretching vibration (3200 cm^{-1}) and C=O stretching vibration (1660 cm^{-1}) in the infra red spectrum.

2-Substituted-3-[β -{N-Substituted piperidyl}] ethyl indoles :

To a stirred mixture of LiAlH_4 (1 gm) in 1,2-dimethoxy ethane (dry, 50 ml) was added 2-substituted piperidyl indole 3-yl glyoxylamide (0.005 mole) in small portions at such a rate, as to keep the reaction temperature below 35° . The reaction mixture was refluxed for 18 hours, cooled to -5° . Excess LiAlH_4 was decomposed by dropwise addition of H_2O , the inorganic material was filtered off and the filtrate evaporated to a solid. It was recrystallized with appropriate solvent. The melting points, recrystallisation solvents and other analytical data are given in Table 2. Compounds No. 12, 16 and 17 in Table 2 showed the characteristic bands of—NH stretching vibration (3300 cm^{-1}) in the infra red spectrum, the C=O stretching band was completely absent.

Biological studies :

Dogs were anaesthetized with pentobarbitone sodium (30 mg/kg) maintained on positive pressure

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TABLE 1—2-SUBSTITUTED-N'-(SUBSTITUTED PIPERIDYL)-INDOLE-3-YL GLYOXYLAMIDES(I)

Sl. No.	R	R ₁	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	% Nitrogen Calcd.	% Nitrogen Found	Dose mg/kg IVI	% Change in B. P. (a)	Effect of CO and NA responses
1.	H	4-OH,4-C ₆ H ₅	180	70	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₃	8.04	8.01	3	-	No effect
2.	H	2-CH ₃	165	75	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	10.37	10.32	3	-9.1	"
3.	H	3-CH ₃	160	80	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	10.37	10.41	2	-	"
4.	H	3-OH	178	65	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₃	10.29	10.25	2	-	"
5.	CH ₃	2-CH ₃	185	70	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₃	9.85	9.83	2	-	"
6.	CH ₃	3-CH ₃	181	75	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₃	9.85	9.89	2	-	"
7.	CH ₃	3-OH	192	65	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₃	9.79	9.84	2	-	"
8.	CH ₃	4-OH,4-C ₆ H ₅	178	65	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₃	7.73	7.79	2	-	"
9.	C ₆ H ₅	4-OH,4-C ₆ H ₅	166	80	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₃	6.60	6.68	3	-	"
10.	C ₆ H ₅	2-CH ₃	184	75	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₃	8.09	8.02	2	-	"

(a) % change in blood pressure as compared to control. — indicates decrease in blood pressure
+ indicates increase in blood pressure

TABLE 2—2-SUBSTITUTED-3-[β-{N'-(SUBSTITUTED PIPERIDYL)} ETHYL] INDOLE(II)

Sl. No.	R	R ₁	M.P. °C	Yield %	Recryst. solvent	Molecular formula	% Nitrogen Calcd.	% Nitrogen Found	Dose mg/kg IVI	% Change in B. P. (b)	Effect of CO and NA responses
11.	H	4-OH,4-C ₆ H ₅	110	35	E-C	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ N ₂ O	8.75	8.72	2	-	No effect
12.	H	2-CH ₃	124	30	A	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ N ₂	11.57	11.51	3	-13.2	"
13.	H	3-CH ₃	120	40	A	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ N ₂	11.57	11.59	3	-	"
14.	H	3-OH	145	35	A	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ N ₂ O	11.48	11.42	2	-	"
15.	CH ₃	2-CH ₃	154	30	E-C	C ₁₇ H ₂₄ N ₂	10.80	10.80	2	-	"
16.	CH ₃	3-CH ₃	128	35	E-C	C ₁₇ H ₂₄ N ₂	10.82	10.88	2	+22.5	"
17.	CH ₃	3-OH	136	30	E-C	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ N ₂ O	10.74	10.71	2	+16.8	"
18.	CH ₃	4-OH,4-C ₆ H ₅	120	35	E-C	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₂ O	8.38	8.32	2	-	"
19.	C ₆ H ₅	4-OH,4-C ₆ H ₅	142	30	C	C ₂₇ H ₂₈ N ₂ O	7.14	7.14	3	-19.07	"
20.	C ₆ H ₅	2-CH ₃	122	40	B	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₂	8.84	8.80	3	-	"

(a) A-Ethanol, B-Methanol, C-Acetone, E-Ether

(b) % change in blood pressure as compared to control — indicates decrease in blood pressure
+ indicates increase in blood pressure

artificial respiration. The blood pressure (B. P.) was recorded from the common carotid artery through a mercury manometer on kymograph paper. Drugs were administered through cannulated right femoral vein. The effect of compounds was studied on resting B. P. and on pressor responses evoked either by carotid occlusion (CO) for 10-30 seconds or by 1.2 μg/kg of noradrenaline (NA) given intravenously.

Results and Discussion

The cardiovascular effects of this group of compounds are summarised in Table 1 and 2. Out of 20 compounds tested, only compounds 2, 12 and 19 elicited a mild hypotensive activity without affecting the CO and NA response. Compounds 16 and 17 on the other hand induced a short lasting hypertensive response. The remaining fifteen compounds failed to exhibit any cardiovascular effects in the doses tested.

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References

- E. SCHITLER and H. J. BEIN, In *Antihypertensive Agents*, E. Schlittler ed. Academic Press, New York, 1967, 191, 221.
- M. M. RAPPORT, A. A. GREEN, J. M. PAGE, *Science*, 1948, 108, 329.
- M. M. RAPPORT, *M.M.J. Biol. Chem.*, 1948, 180, 961.
- K. E. HAMLIN and F. E. FISHER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 5007.
- M. E. SPECTOR, R. V. HEINZELMANN and R. I. WEISBLAT, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 5514.
- (a) R. V. HEINZELMANN and J. SZMUSKOVIC, *Proc. Drugs Res.*, 1963, 6, 75.
(b) D. J. TRIGGLE in *Medicinal Chemistry*, Vol. 2, 3rd ed. A. Burger Ed. Wiley Interscience, New York, 1970, p. 1283.
(c) A. BURGER in Ref. 6b, pp. 1517-1521.
- J. L. ARCHIBALD, *Chim. Ther.*, 1968, 3, 397.
- J. L. ARCHIBALD, E. J. ALAPS, J. F. CAVALLA, and J. L. JACKSON, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1971, 14, 1054.
- R. B. ROYDS, *Brit. J. Pharmacol.*, 1972, 44, 379.
- C. T. DOLLERY, C. F. GEORGE and P. J. LEWIS, *Brit. J. Pharmacol.*, 1972, 46, 542.
- A. J. BEAKES, B. N. C. PRICHARD and P. C. TECH, *Brit. J. Pharmacol.*, 1972, 44, 378.
- D. J. CALTART, J. D. F. LOCKHART, R. B. ROYDS and P. TURNER, *Brit. J. Pharmacol.*, 1971, 43, 467.
- R. L. SHRINER, W. C. ASHLEY and E. WELCH, *Organic Synthesis*, 1948, 22, 98.
- A. I. VOGEL, 1971, I, 851, A Text book of Practical Organic Chemistry.
- M. E. SPECTOR and W. C. ANTHONY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 6208.
- A. F. AMER, D. E. AMES, C. R. COYNE, T. F. GREY, I. M. LOCKHART and R. S. RALPH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 3388.